

Synthesis of Lengthened Sulphur Chain Compounds.

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When alcoholic potassium hydrosulphide acts upon trimethylene dibromide (Hagelberg, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1085 ; Austenrieth and Wolff, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1369) the main product of reaction is the mercaptan $\text{SH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SH}$ which can be separated from the reaction mixture by steam distillation.

The residue on acidification with dilute sulphuric acid gave an oil which after purification boiled at $180^\circ/40$ mm. In view of the interesting by-products obtained by Rây (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 134) in the preparation of dithioethylene glycol, we thought it desirable to examine this compound. The constitution of the compound, from analytical data and chemical properties, appears to be $\text{SH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{S}\cdot\text{S}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SH}$, which is probably formed by the partial oxidation of 1:3-dithiopropylene glycol.

We attempted to prove the constitution of the compound definitely by synthesis. Our plan was to protect one of the thiol groups of the thioglycol, oxidise the compound and finally remove the protecting groups. Thus:— $\text{RS}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SH} \rightarrow \text{RS}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{S}\cdot\text{S}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SR} \rightarrow \text{SH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{S}\cdot\text{S}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SH}$.

With this object in view, we attempted to acetylate the mercaptan partially by the direct action of acetic anhydride on the mercaptan. The product of the reaction under a variety of conditions was always found to be the disubstituted compound which was obtained in rather poor yield. In presence of pyridine however, the yield increased from 14 % to 88 %. The ester was then hydrolysed by 15% caustic potash solution at the room temperature when the desired mono-ester $\text{AcS}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SH}$ was obtained. This was oxidised by iodine in ethereal solution to the disulphide and subsequently the acetyl groups were removed by hydrolysis with potassium hydroxide solution on the water-bath. The dimercaptan thus obtained appeared to be identical with the compound isolated from the products of interaction of trimethylene dibromide and potassium hydrosulphide. In this connection, it was found that

178°/50 mm. (yield, 88%). (Found: C, 43·4; H, 6·38; S, 31·85; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 189. $C_7H_{12}S_2O_2$ requires C, 43·6; H, 6·25; S, 33·33 per cent.; M. W. 192.)

The substance is a bright lemon-yellow liquid, b. p. 255°, possessing a peculiar ester-like smell. It is insoluble in water but very soluble in the common organic solvents. It decomposes on continued boiling.

Monoacetyl-1:3-dithiopropylene glycol, $CH_3CO \cdot S \cdot (CH_2)_3 \cdot SH$.

—The mercaptan (47 gm.) and potassium hydroxide (31 gm. in 200 c.c. of water) were shaken vigorously in an electric shaker for 18 hours at the room temperature (28°—30°). The solution was then neutralised with hydrochloric acid, and the emulsion thus formed was extracted by means of ether.

The ethereal extract, after dehydration by means of anhydrous sodium sulphate was distilled under reduced pressure, in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. At about 70° 1:3-dithiopropylene glycol which was partly produced in the process of hydrolysis, distilled over. At 115°—116°/40 mm. the mono-acetylated compound distilled over. (Yield 21·8%). (Found: C, 39·87; H, 6·60; S, 40·49; SH (by iodine), 0·9.; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 145; 141. $C_5H_{10}OS_2$ requires C, 40·0; H, 6·66; S, 42·66 per cent.; SH, 1); M. W., 150.

Monoacetyl-1:3-dithiopropylene glycol is a light yellow liquid having a sweet ester-like smell quite distinct from that of the parent mercaptan. It is insoluble in water, but is miscible in all proportions with common organic solvents. It decolorises iodine, and on long standing gradually decomposes, when smell of 1:3-dithiopropylene glycol is evolved. It also readily forms insoluble compounds with mercuric chloride and mercurous nitrite, etc. and gives coloration with lead acetate papers.

Diacetyl derivative of Hexamethylene Disulphide Dimercaptan, $CH_3CO \cdot S \cdot (CH_2)_3 \cdot S \cdot S \cdot (CH_2)_3 \cdot S \cdot COCH_3$.

Monoacetyldithiopropylene glycol in ethereal solution was shaken with the gradual addition of solid iodine, at the room temperature, until the coloration of iodine was persistent. The excess of iodine was removed by a little sodium thiosulphate solution. The ethereal solution was then washed several times with water and finally with dilute sodium carbonate solution. After drying the solution and removal of ether, the product was obtained as an oil. (Found: C, 39·91; H, 5·82; M. W. (cryoscopic

in benzene) 274, 280. $C_{10}H_{18}O_2S_4$ requires C, 40.26 ; H, 6.04 per cent. ; M.W., 298).

The ester is a mobile yellowish liquid possessing a peculiar characteristic odour. It is insoluble in water but soluble in common organic solvents. It decomposes at ordinary atmospheric pressure at a temperature below its b.p.

Hexamethylene Disulphide Dimercaptan, $SH(CH_2)_3S(CH_2)_3SH$.

Diacetyl hexamethylene disulphide dimercaptan was heated with an excess of potassium hydroxide (15% soln.) on the water-bath. The resulting product was then acidified with hydrochloric acid which liberated the mercaptan. This was finally extracted by means of ether and the disulphide dimercaptan was obtained as an oil after removing the ether on the water-bath under reduced pressure. (Found: C, 32.1 ; H, 6.88 ; S, 58.38 ; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 200 ; SH (by iodine), 1.8. $C_6H_{14}S_2$ requires C, 33.6 ; H, 6.3 ; S, 59.8 per cent. ; M. W., 214 ; SH, 2).

The mercaptan thus obtained is a yellow mobile liquid like the by-product obtained in the preparation of 1:3-dithiopropylene glycol, and possesses an unpleasant smell characteristic of mercaptans. It boils at 258° at ordinary pressure and forms orange and white insoluble precipitates with oxides of lead and mercury respectively. It is insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in alcohol, but completely miscible with common organic solvents.

Diacetyldithioethylene glycol, $CH_3CO\cdot S(CH_2)_2S\cdot COCH_3$.—This was obtained in quantitative yield from dithioethylene glycol and acetic anhydride in the way mentioned before. It crystallised from alcohol in the form of white needles, m. p. 60°. It is soluble in most organic solvents. (Found: C, 40.16 ; H, 5.8 ; S, 34.1. $C_6H_{10}O_2S_2$ requires C, 40.45 ; H, 5.61 ; S, 35.94 per cent.).

Monoacetyldithioethylene glycol, $CH_3CO\cdot S(CH_2)_2\cdot SH$.—This was obtained by the hydrolysis of the diacetyl derivative (cf. preparation of monoacetyl-1:3-dithiopropylene glycol) for 12 hours. The product after purification was obtained as a colourless oil, b. p. 95°-97°/40 mm. (Found: C, 35.59 ; H, 6.12 ; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 130. $C_4H_8S_2O$ requires C, 35.29 ; H, 5.38 per cent. ; M.W., 136).

It possesses a peculiar ester-like smell. It is insoluble in water but soluble in common organic solvents. On long standing it gives a smell of dithioethylene glycol. It decolorises iodine, and forms

insoluble compounds with lead oxide, mercuric chloride and mercurous nitrite.

Diacetyl derivative of Tetramethylene Disulphide Dimercaptan, $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}\cdot\text{S}(\text{CH}_2)_2\cdot\text{S}\cdot\text{S}\cdot(\text{CH}_2)_2\cdot\text{S}\cdot\text{COCH}_3$.-- This compound was prepared like the corresponding diacetylhexamethylene disulphide dimercaptan, by treatment of the mono-acetylated product ($\text{CH}_3\text{CO}\cdot\text{S}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{S}\cdot\text{H}$) with iodine. The pure compound was obtained as a colourless oil. (Found: C, 35.4; H, 5.37; S, 45.72; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene) 250. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}_4$ requires C, 35.55; H, 5.19; S, 47.4 per cent.; M. W., 270).

The substance when treated with dilute aqueous alkali on the water-bath decomposed completely. On treatment with 15% sodium carbonate solution a yellowish oil, b. p. 180° was obtained. The yield was insufficient for purification, analysis, and further studies.

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